

SOCIO-POLITICAL EMPOWERMENT OF SCHEDULED CASTES

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Abstract

This paper provides an overview of the transformation in socio-political status of the Scheduled caste community. It also discusses change in the course of dalit movement and impact of applicability and outcomes of the schemes launched by the Central government and various state governments for empowerment of the said community. It also provides an overview of the role played by Schedule Caste commission for the protection of SC community against atrocities and discrimination. The paper concludes by reviewing present approaches and ways forward for the transformation of Socio-economic status of Scheduled caste.

Introduction

Traditionally for a long time in history, the scheduled castes have been neglected from almost every political role and were put on the last strata of Social hierarchy. There was a class even below them, who were socially excluded, broadly considered as 'Antyaj' or 'Atishudras'. Political assertion of Dalit (NCERT,2007) is considered to be started in the 1970s by most of the research scholars, but some traces are found of starting of robust dalit movement in the 1920's Adi-hindu movement in Western and Central U.P. by swami achhutanand. The movement were ignored in the dalit history because they were non-ambedkarite and followed apposite path from anti-british freedom movement started by dominant congress party in pre-independence and post-independence era. (Swaroop, 1995, Ravat, 2015). The adi-hindu movement was anti-hindi and supported british rule. As In 1999, the Dalit political commentator Chandra Bhan Prasad argued "The British came too late but left too early", is against majority indian sentiments, So they were treated as marginalised. (Campion, 2015)

A talk at Labdon School of Economics, Dr Ramnarayan S Rawat articulately challenged assumptions of dalit politics. Drawing on research undertaken for his book "Reconsidering Untouchability: Chamars and Dalit History in North India", he traced a chain of vibrant Dalit movements in Uttar Pradesh (UP), from the Adi Hindu Mahasabha in the 1920s- 1940s to the Bahujan Samaj Party (BSP) today. At the heart of this sustained activism has been concern among Dalit groups for equality and dignity.

Before the simon commission's enquiry, Ambedkar was against separate identity politics and demands of separate electorate for Dalits. After representing dalits before the Simon commission, he emerged as the supreme leader of Dalits. After the Round table conference he moved towards redical and extreme anti-hindu dalit movement. This was the turning point of dalit politics in India, that became guidance principle for all dalit leaders in india. After his death, dalit movement deprived of a centalized and national dalit leadership. This broke dalit politics into many regional interests, who followed different type of political ideologies and dalit leaders. Many merged in the Congress system, remaining limited themselves to regional aspirations only and becoming puppets to locally dominant political parties. In the influence

of Black panther movement of America, Anti- apartheid movement of Africa and Maoist communist movement in China and East asian countries, Indian dalit movement revived in 1970's. End of Congress dominance system after Nehru, crisis of demand and supply in government formation catalyzed political congregation of Scheduled castes and Backward castes. This new trend in India politics was linked to economic restructuring and demand for redistribution of opportunities. Gradual change in traditional visheshadhikar and dominance resulted into politicization of social diversity and empowerment of downtrodden scheduled castes and other backward communities. The castes which were stronger in the land possession or educationally stronger emerged as the flag bearers of Dalit movement. Population census 1901 confirms more than 90% chamars were depend for livelihood on agricultural and semi-agricultural activities, just like them mahars were more leaning to empowerment through education and government jobs, this made them much superior to other dalit caste. (Simon commission report 1927, Lothian committee report 1931). In this way, the role played by caste in Politics helped in modernisation of the political structure of the caste system, better distribution of economic resources and politicization and socio-political empowerment of caste. But this empowerment benefited more only to a small fraction of castes, which divides the scheduled castes into 3 categories i.e. A. Elite castes B. Middle castes and C. Neglected castes. As in U.P., Chamars and Koris benefited more , in Maharashtra, Mahars and Neo-buddists the same thing applies to other states. In U.P. Mayawati was the first C.M. from dalit community who ruled the states from 3 terms, but it is observed that she failed in the social and economic empowerment of dalits. At this time she has lost all his seats in vidhan sabha.

At the time of independence 15% of the total population of the country and approximately 95% of the population below poverty-line. There are 1263 castes as specified in the country (the handbook on social welfare statistics 2016 of the Ministry of Social Justice and empowerment). A large portion of them have been usually engaged in unpleasant and menial jobs. It is in this segment of society that one finds greater illiteracy, poorer health, poorer nutrition, poorer housing as well as exploitation by large landholders generally the upper caste and Middle level castes, money lenders, village traders and businessmen etc. Most of the benefits received through the reservation system and other special provisions for empowerment of dalits are grabbed by the dalit elites, and the lowest section gets deprived of the benefits and depends on the elites of the community.

Numerical Representation in Legislatures

The population figure of SCs in relation to the total population figure had increased from 14.6% in the 1971 census to 16.2% in the 2001 census. The overall increase in the population of SCs and STs in the 2001 census has led the Delimitation Commission 2008 to increase the seats for Scheduled castes in Lok Sabha from 79 to 84. Due to the delimitation, in Bihar, Chattisgarh, and Uttar Pradesh seats reserved for SCs have been decreased. It increased in Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Punjab and West Bengal. (mea.gov.in 2009, loksabhadocs.nic.in 2016)

Empowerment of the socially disadvantaged groups such as scheduled castes continues to be the priority list of the country's development agenda. The framers of the Constitution made arrangements for equal status in the society and empowered the state to make special provisions for the advancement of socially, economically and educationally backward classes people. Article 46 of the Indian Constitution directs the Indian government to provide social economic and political justice and equality of status and opportunity to all citizens and provides safeguards and protective measures for the development of SCs.

Development of SCs

A number of initiatives have been taken by the Government for development of SCs, which have yielded positive outcomes, and have also resulted in narrowing the gaps between the Scheduled Castes and the rest of the population.

From 2017-18 onwards, Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment has been entrusted with the task of monitoring the physical and financial outcome of Schemes under Development Action Plan for Scheduled Castes (DAPSC) erstwhile Scheduled Caste Sub Plan (SCSP)/ Allocation for Welfare of Scheduled Castes(AWSC) in respect of concerned 41 Central Ministries and Departments.

The Allocation for Welfare of Scheduled Castes was stepped up from Rs.62,473.86 crores in 2018-19 to Rs.81340.74 crores in 2019-20, an increase of about 30.20%. But The representation of Scheduled caste MPs in three important parliamentary committees that are responsible for economic well being and distribution of financial resources, is very less; and The SC MPs rarely attend and participate in the committees. This neglecting behavior of the representatives of Scheduled castes is responsible for meagre financial allocation to the issues of dalits.

Abolition of Untouchability

The Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955 provides punishment for the practice of untouchability. This act is a major tool to protect SCs against age old discrimination and harassment by the Upper castes, but some recent cases shows that Caste still matters and practice of Untouchability hasn't ended yet. Such as- Sambhava community case of Kozhikode district (2019), Shri Jatadhari 'Devasthanam' of Kasargod remains shut for three years after untouchables demand dignity, few months ago President of India also faced an incident of Untouchability while offering prayers in Kanpur etc.

Empirical studies say that the practice of Untouchability is diminishing with the growing educational reach, cohesive nature of caste politics and most importantly urbanization.

The practice of 'untouchability' – the prohibition of social and relational interaction between Dalit and other communities – further limited their possibilities for upward mobility. In spite of legal measures that penalized such practices after independence, caste-based exclusion continued to prevail.

Education and Employability

With the support of reservation policy, SC are getting placed in schools and colleges, but they have to face hindrances and challenges by upper and middle castes fellow students. As per the 66th round report of NSSO, the empowerment of scheduled caste through education also seems to have so far not resulted in any significant change since the gap has remained almost constant. Enrollment ratio of SC students opting for Diploma courses between 1999-2000 and 2011-12 has reduced by 75% (29/1000 to 7/1000). Number of SC students in graduate and Post-graduate courses has also fallen from 54/1000 to 37/1000 in the same period.

With such a low proportion of scheduled caste graduates and diploma holders the rise of scheduled caste to higher socioeconomic level in the society does not appear feasible as access to higher and better paying jobs to the majority of the SC population will not be possible. The unemployment thus created due to lack of skilled higher education affects SC women more severely. For example- all the seats reserved for SC women in the Vacancy for assistant professor of Dharma Shastra subject in BSUSC, Bihar could not be grabbed by them.

Due to poverty and lack of awareness, a large number of SC students leave their studies before high school. There is a very small educated and professionally qualified layer in the SC Population. Only 44 out of every 1000 SC can have access to the skilled and comparative higher paying jobs as they have either degrees or diplomas and thus have only to the most menial and low paid jobs.

Education and Employability are directly proportional to each other. Comparative analysis of Census 2001 and 2011 shows that 1.15% SC population has shifted from main work-force to marginal work-force.

Socio-economic status of most of the SC population hinders progress of the community in government jobs, condition is worse in the private and unorganized sector due to caste discrimination and caste-oriented dominance in different skill-based works, Social stigmatization is a major negative factor. For example- A Brahmin can not be accepted socially to work as a Cobbler or a Sweeper, same as A Mehtar can't be accepted as priest of a temple or owner of a hotel.

As per the socio-economic caste census 2011, the representation of SCs in our country is still very negligible. Only 0.45% of SC households have jobs in the private sector where 3.56% of the total households have shops in the private sector. This is very low as compared to others.

Most of the Indian states have less than 2% participation of SC households in private sector jobs.

Surprisingly surprisingly the number of persons registered in the employment exchange has risen but the placement percentage of SC remains almost static. SC community shares the largest share of MGNREGA, this is because more than 85% of SCs either have very small agricultural land to plough or are working at someone's land as agricultural laborers.

Dalit entrepreneurship - for the Dalit community, nayi soch requires it to shed old shibboleths about entrepreneurship and private enterprise and embrace it rather than treat it as a Baniya activity. Only then will the promise of Dalit entrepreneurship be fully realized.

Land Ownership

According to the National family health survey 2005-06, scheduled caste holds only 8.6 % of the land holding and the average size of these Holdings is also much lower. Moreover 54.7% of SC households are landless and work as manual casual labor. Similar findings come out of agriculture census 2010-11 which states that only 58 % of the total SC population have cemented houses whereas the General population have 87% pakka houses. The SC population has mud houses approximately three times more than the others. Governments have launched different schemes to build cemented well finished houses for all, but that hasn't been much useful for them because 1. That number of houses are meager in comparison to the number of needy candidates, 2. The colonies built were far from the marketplace or work place. So they could not be helpful in the transformation of the socio-economic status of SCs. While making plans for the community, the states should give priority to schemes which provide basic minimum services like primary education, health, drinking water, nutrition, rural housing, link roads and electrification of SC villages, so they could ensure self-reliance using the resources provided as such. Most of the government allocates funds in the name of upliftment of SCs, but the fund is spent on general schemes. So a greater share of benefit is consumed by the Others not by the dalits. So funds of SCs should be spent on SC dedicated infrastructure and other services.

SC Women

SC women are much underprivileged than that of the SC male. Crimes against all women are on a rise but dalit women suffer the double discrimination of gender and caste. These women also become easy pawns for revenge in fights between men.

Dalit women of India have been living in the culture of silence throughout the centuries. They have remained mute expectators to their exploitation, oppression and barbarity against them. They do not have any control over their own bodies, earnings, and lives. The extreme expression of violence, exploitation and oppression against them is visible in forms of hunger, malnutrition, disease, physical and mental torture, rape; illiteracy, ill-health, unemployment, insecurity and inhuman treatment. The collective forces of Feudalism, Casteism, and patriarchy have made their lives just a hell. An overwhelming majority of them live under the most precarious conditions. In the present age of modernism and postmodernism they are still living in a darker age of savagery.

The SC women have to face severest form of problems as faced by women of 'others' and SC men. They lack economic resources, dual-patriarchy, educational deprivation, burden of household chores, and the most heinous sexual offenses. Across India, cases of rape against SC women increased by 37%, and of assault by 20%, as IndiaSpend reported based on data from Crime in India 2019. Further, 32.5% crimes against scheduled castes across India were not registered under Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act 1989 between 2009 and 2018, according to the National Campaign on Dalit Human Rights (NCDHR) status report, Implementation of SCs and STs (PoA) Act 1989 and Rules 1995, launched in September 2020. UP recorded the highest increase in crime against women, 66.7%, over the four years to 2019, and the second highest increase in cases of rape against Scheduled Castes (SC) women in the same period--20.67%.

Along with this, the judiciary is also not performing well on the human rights of Scheduled castes. The reasons behind are many, but most prominent is the representation of SCs in Judiciary.

According to the report on Scheduled caste in judiciary published by the Schedule caste commission, the current structure of Judiciary doesn't align with the national interests of Social equality and Justice. The Parliament report 2000 put by Karia munda states the very underrepresented status of SCs in Supreme court and High courts. Referring to authoritative sources –reports by the Kariya Munda Committee, a parliamentary committee on the welfare of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (2000); the National Commission to Review the Working of the Constitution, chaired by Justice M.N. Venkatachaliah (2002); the Parliamentary Standing Committee under the chairmanship of Dr E.M. Sudarsana Natchiappan (2006); and the National Commission for Scheduled Castes (2016) — the report says that as of 2011, there were only 24 judges belonging to Scheduled Caste (SC)/Scheduled Tribe (ST) against a total of 850 judges in all the 21 High Courts. It further laments that today, while only two of the 33 Supreme Court judges are Dalit.

Even after independence, Dalits could not assert their political will themselves, they had to depend on regionally dominant political parties led by others (Badrinarayana, 2018). There had been an absence of an effective national level dalit leadership after Dr ambedkar, this result into backwardness of scheduled castes. Today they lack unified goals, unified strategy and unified leadership also.

It is said that Dalit can be empowered only if they are led by a dalit leader. Political philosophy of Dalit movement is now transforming from Ambedkarite peaceful movement to

Neo-buddist movement on the principle of "of Dalits, for Dalits and By Dalits". (Illaiah, 2007)

Conclusion

From the independence time till now, Condition of SCs has been much better, from the political stupny for regional dominant parties to the steering wheel of Government making. They have to face a lack of even basic necessities. Backwardness in education makes the transformation in socio-economic status of SCs nearly impossible themselves. So it is clear that the government should take serious steps vigilantly, so that empowerment of SCs can be ensured. Representation of the SCs should also be increased in Legislature, Executive and most importantly in Judiciary.

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